

Research Article

Computational and Molecular Docking Analysis of β -Sitosterol from Turmeric as a Potential Therapeutic Agent for Ulcerative Colitis

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ABSTRACT

Ulcerative colitis (UC) is a chronic inflammatory disorder of the colon characterized by recurrent mucosal ulceration, diarrhea, abdominal pain, and weight loss. Conventional therapies, including aminosalicylates, corticosteroids, and immunosuppressants, provide symptomatic relief but are often associated with adverse effects and incomplete remission. In recent years, natural phytochemicals have gained attention as alternative or complementary therapeutic options. β -Sitosterol, a bioactive phytosterol abundantly present in turmeric, has demonstrated anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory properties. Emerging evidence suggests that β -sitosterol exerts its effects by modulating the NF- κ B signaling pathway and activating peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor- γ (PPAR- γ), thereby reducing pro-inflammatory cytokine expression and restoring intestinal homeostasis. In this study, molecular docking was employed to predict the binding affinity and interaction patterns of β -sitosterol with key UC-related targets. The docking simulations revealed favorable binding energies, supported by hydrogen bonding, hydrophobic interactions, and van der Waals forces, indicating strong protein–ligand interactions. These findings suggest that β -sitosterol could serve as a promising lead compound for the development of safer and more effective therapeutics for UC. Further in vitro and in vivo studies are required to validate its therapeutic potential.

INTRODUCTION

Ulcerative colitis (UC) is a chronic inflammatory disorder of the colon and rectum, marked by recurrent episodes of mucosal inflammation and ulceration. Patients often experience diarrhea, rectal bleeding, abdominal pain, weight loss, and

persistent fatigue¹. Despite significant progress in conventional therapies, achieving and maintaining long-term remission remains a challenge. In severe cases, surgical intervention, including total proctocolectomy, becomes necessary (1–3). Current treatments primarily involve aminosalicylates, corticosteroids, and

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immunosuppressants, which, while effective in symptom control, are often associated with adverse effects and limited efficacy (4).

In recent years, interest in complementary and alternative therapies for UC has grown considerably. Among these, turmeric, a spice widely used in Asian cuisine and valued for its medicinal properties, has shown promising potential. Turmeric contains several bioactive compounds (5–7), which have been reported to reduce intestinal inflammation and alleviate UC-related symptoms. However, despite its popularity, the available scientific evidence supporting turmeric's therapeutic efficacy in UC remains limited and inconclusive (8).

One notable bioactive component in turmeric is β -sitosterol, a naturally occurring phytosterol abundant in fruits, vegetables, and nuts (9,10). Multiple studies have investigated its anti-inflammatory effects (11). Recent findings (2023) demonstrate that β -sitosterol attenuates inflammatory responses by inhibiting the NF- κ B signaling pathway (12,13). Moreover, peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor- γ (PPAR- γ), highly expressed in the colon, has emerged as a critical therapeutic target in UC. Activation of PPAR- γ suppresses NF- κ B activity and, in turn, downregulates pro-inflammatory cytokine production (14). Additionally, a study by Liyuan Ma et al. (2023) revealed that β -sitosterol could modulate gut microbiota composition, thereby preventing allergic responses in mice (15).

Alongside experimental approaches, computational drug discovery has become increasingly important in predicting interactions between small molecules and target proteins (16). Molecular docking software, such as AutoDock,(17), plays a key role in this process by modeling the orientation and binding affinity of ligands within protein active sites. Docking

analysis evaluates multiple interactions—including shape complementarity, electrostatic forces, van der Waals interactions, Coulombic forces, and hydrogen bonding—to estimate binding potential. The overall score obtained reflects the likelihood of stable binding, providing valuable insights for identifying lead compounds in drug design (18).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Preparation of protein and ligands optimization.

1. **ChemSketch:** Used to design and visualize 2D and 3D structures of the ligands. The software also facilitated structural optimization and molecular property predictions.
2. **PubChem:** Ligand structures and corresponding bioactivity data were retrieved in standard formats (SDF, MOL, or PDB) for subsequent modification and analysis.
3. **Protein Data Bank (PDB):** Protein structures were obtained and pre-processed by removing water molecules, adding hydrogen atoms, and assigning appropriate charges to ensure accuracy in docking studies.
4. **BIOVIA Discovery Studio:** Utilized to optimize receptor structures, identify active binding sites, and assist in preliminary molecular docking to evaluate binding affinities.
5. **OpenBabel:** Applied for chemical file format conversion and ligand geometry optimization, ensuring compatibility across various docking platforms.
6. **AutoDock Suite:**
 - a. *AutoDock 4.2:* Conducted flexible ligand docking using the Lamarckian Genetic Algorithm (LGA).
 - b. *AutoDock Vina:* Delivered rapid and accurate docking simulations with improved scoring functions.

c. *AutoGrid*: Generated grid maps by computing receptor–ligand interaction energies for docking calculations.

7. **Command Prompt (CMD)**: Employed to automate docking workflows, execute file conversions, and extract docking scores for post-analysis.

Figure 1: 3D Structure of beta sitosterol

Figure 2: 3D Structure interaction of beta sitosterol with 3GBK protein

The 3D docking analysis revealed that β -sitosterol fits stably within the active pocket of 3GBK (human carbonic anhydrase II), where its bulky hydrophobic sterol backbone is surrounded by residues such as Leu198, Val121, Leu141, Phe131, Val143, and Trp209, forming extensive van der Waals and hydrophobic interactions. The terminal hydroxyl group of β -sitosterol established a weak hydrogen bond with Thr199/Thr200, while the steroid core oriented near the His94–His96–His119 zinc-binding triad without direct Zn^{2+} coordination. This binding mode suggests that β -sitosterol may interfere with substrate access to the catalytic site through steric hindrance and hydrophobic stabilization, supporting its predicted

high affinity but non-classical inhibition mechanism.(19,20)

Table 1: Docking-predicted biological characteristics of ligand (Beta sitosterol and *Standard mesalamine and budesonide drug) with 3GBK protein

Ligand	Docking score
Beta sitosterol	-9.1
Mesalamine*	-5.0
Budesonide*	-7.3

Docking analysis revealed that β -sitosterol exhibited the strongest predicted binding affinity (-9.1 kcal/mol), primarily through a favorable hydrophobic fit within the active site. However, its poor solubility and low absorption may limit its practical therapeutic potential. Budesonide demonstrated a good binding affinity (-7.3

kcal/mol) with a balanced interaction profile, and when combined with its favorable ADME properties, it emerges as the most viable candidate. In contrast, mesalamine showed weaker binding (-5.0 kcal/mol), which is consistent with its role as a locally acting anti-inflammatory agent in the gut rather than a potent systemic binder. Overall, the results suggest that while β -sitosterol has the

strongest theoretical affinity and may interact stably via hydrophobic contacts with limited hydrogen bonding, budesonide remains the most drug-like option, and mesalamine aligns with its established localized therapeutic mechanism.

Assessment of ADME properties and Docking studies.

Table 2: Analysis of Physicochemical, Pharmacokinetic, and Drug-Likeness Properties of Ligands and Standard

Molecule	BETA SITOSTEROL	MESALAMINE (REFERENCE)	BUDESONIDE (REFERENCE)
Canonical SMILES	<chem>CCC(C(C)C)CCC(C1C CC2C1(C)CCC1C2CC=C2C1(C)CCC(C2)O)C</chem>	<chem>C1=CC(=C(C=C1N)C(=O)O)O</chem>	<chem>OCC(=O)[C@H]1[C@H](C[C@H]2[C@]1(C)C[C@H](O)[C@]1([C@H]2CCC2=C(C(=O)C=C[C@]12C)C(=O)C</chem>
Formula	C29H50O	C7H7NO3	C24H32O5
MW	414.71	153.14	400.51
#Heavy atoms	30	11	29
#Aromatic heavy atoms	0	6	0
Fraction Csp3	0.93	0	0.71
#Rotatable bonds	6	1	3
#H-bond acceptors	1	3	5
#H-bond donors	1	3	2
MR	133.23	39.83	110.22
TPSA	20.23	83.55	91.67
iLOGP	4.79	0.6	2.22
XLOGP3	9.34	0.5	1.75
WLOGP	8.02	0.68	2.65
MLOGP	6.73	-0.7	1.86
Silicos-IT Log P	7.04	0.02	3.13
Consensus Log P	7.19	0.22	2.32
ESOL Log S	-7.9	-1.44	-3.23
ESOL Solubility (mg/ml)	5.23E-06	5.53E+00	2.37E-01
ESOL Solubility (mol/l)	1.26E-08	3.61E-02	5.92E-04
ESOL Class	Poorly soluble	Very soluble	Soluble
Ali Log S	-9.67	-1.82	-3.29
Ali Solubility (mg/ml)	8.90E-08	2.29E+00	2.04E-01
Ali Solubility (mol/l)	2.15E-10	1.50E-02	5.10E-04
Ali Class	Poorly soluble	Very soluble	Soluble
Silicos-IT LogSw	-6.19	-0.82	-3.2
Silicos-IT Solubility (mg/ml)	2.69E-04	2.31E+01	2.51E-01
Silicos-IT Solubility (mol/l)	6.49E-07	1.51E-01	6.27E-04
Silicos-IT class	Poorly soluble	Soluble	Soluble
GI absorption	Low	High	High

BBB permeant	No	No	No
Pgp substrate	No	No	Yes
CYP1A2 inhibitor	No	No	No
CYP2C19 inhibitor	No	No	No
CYP2C9 inhibitor	No	No	No
CYP2D6 inhibitor	No	No	No
CYP3A4 inhibitor	No	No	No
log Kp (cm/s)	-2.2	-6.88	-7.5
Lipinski #violations	1	0	0
Ghose #violations	3	3	0
Veber #violations	0	0	0
Egan #violations	1	0	0
Muegge #violations	2	1	0
Bioavailability Score	0.55	0.56	0.55
PAINS #alerts	0	0	0
Brenk #alerts	1	2	0
Leadlikeness #violations	2	1	1
Synthetic Accessibility	6.3	1	5.49

β -Sitosterol: Highly lipophilic, extremely poor solubility, predicted low GI absorption. No major CYP or P-gp risks but limited oral bioavailability; requires formulation strategies.

Mesalamine: Very soluble and polar, limited passive permeability. Effective mainly for local intestinal action; colon-targeted formulations preferred.

Budesonide: Moderate lipophilicity, soluble, high GI absorption but P-gp substrate. Good oral/colon-targeted drug profile with controlled release; first-pass metabolism reduces systemic effects.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Docking simulations were carried out to compare the binding affinity of β -sitosterol with the reference drugs budesonide and mesalamine against the 3GBK protein. The analysis revealed a distinct hierarchy in binding potential. β -Sitosterol demonstrated the strongest affinity (-9.1 kcal/mol), primarily due to a favorable hydrophobic fit within the active pocket. It engaged in extensive van der Waals and

hydrophobic interactions with residues Leu198, Val121, Leu141, Val143, Phe131, and Trp209, while its hydroxyl group established a weak hydrogen bond with Thr199/Thr200. Although the sterol core was located near the His94–His96–His119 Zn²⁺ triad, no direct metal coordination occurred, indicating a non-classical inhibition pattern characterized by steric hindrance and hydrophobic stabilization. Budesonide showed a binding energy of -7.3 kcal/mol and maintained a balanced network of hydrophobic and polar interactions. When considered alongside its favorable ADME characteristics, including solubility and oral bioavailability, budesonide emerged as the most practical and drug-like candidate. In contrast, mesalamine exhibited the weakest binding affinity (-5.0 kcal/mol), with only limited polar interactions in the active site, consistent with its known therapeutic role as a locally acting anti-inflammatory agent within the gut rather than a systemic binder.

SwissADME evaluation indicated that β -sitosterol, while exhibiting strong binding affinity, is limited by poor water solubility, high lipophilicity, and low oral absorption, which could

restrict its therapeutic effectiveness *in vivo*. In contrast, budesonide demonstrated favorable pharmacokinetic characteristics, including good gastrointestinal absorption and acceptable drug-likeness, consistent with its established clinical success in managing ulcerative colitis. Mesalamine, although not meeting several drug-likeness criteria, retains clinical relevance owing to its localized action in the colon with minimal systemic uptake. Toxicity assessment using ProTox-II classified β -sitosterol as relatively safe, with no major organ-specific toxicity signals, though its limited bioavailability remains a key drawback.

The results reveal a clear gap between theoretical affinity and practical drug-likeness. Although β -sitosterol binds most strongly receptor, its poor pharmacokinetics limit systemic use unless improved by structural modifications or advanced formulations. Budesonide, with moderate docking strength but superior ADME properties, stands out as the most viable candidate, aligning with its established role in UC treatment. The weak binding of mesalamine supports its function as a locally acting anti-inflammatory. Overall, β -sitosterol may serve as a promising natural scaffold for UC drug development pending experimental validation, while budesonide remains the benchmark therapeutic due to its balanced efficacy and safety.

CONCLUSION:

This study demonstrates that β -sitosterol exhibits the strongest theoretical binding affinity toward the 3GBK receptor, primarily driven by hydrophobic interactions, yet its poor solubility, lipophilicity, and limited absorption significantly restrict its systemic therapeutic potential. Budesonide, although showing moderate docking affinity, combines favorable ADME and safety properties, reaffirming its clinical utility as an

effective UC treatment. Mesalamine, with weak binding, remains relevant due to its localized colonic action rather than systemic receptor inhibition. Collectively, these findings suggest that β -sitosterol holds promise as a natural scaffold for future UC drug development, provided pharmacokinetic limitations are addressed through structural modification or novel delivery systems, while budesonide continues to represent the optimal benchmark therapy.

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